

Gurinerdeutsch Verbal Complex Database (2024)

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Read Me

This package includes the following three files:

- 1) Gurinerdeutsch_VC_Database.xlsx
- 2) Gurinerdeutsch_VC_Database.cvs
- 3) Gurinerdeutsch_VC_ReadMe.pdf

Files 1) and 2) are different versions of the same material.

The material can be cited as follows, including reference to the original published article:

Comrie, Bernard & Frauenfelder, Uli (1992). The verbal complex in Gurinerdeutsch. *Linguistics* 30: 1031–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1992.30.6.1031> Database archived 2024 at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12702341>

Sections 1–3 provide background information and present the structure of the database. Sections 4–5 provide further discussion (in comparison with Comrie & Frauenfelder 1992) on two points of grammatical analysis. Section 6 lists the construction types found in the database and other materials referred to in section 1.

1. Introduction

Gurinerdeutsch is the Walser German dialect of the village Bosco Gurin, Canton Ticino, Switzerland (46°19'N 8°30'E); it falls under ISO 639-3 code: wae, Glottocode: wals1238.

The database, compiled and curated by co-author Comrie, accompanies the following article, which should be consulted for further details, including background information and references:

Comrie, Bernard & Frauenfelder, Uli (1992). The verbal complex in Gurinerdeutsch. *Linguistics* 30: 1031–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ling.1992.30.6.1031>

My original intention was simply to digitize and tidy up the database and make it publicly available, but the enterprise turned out to involve somewhat more work than this, whence the more extensive nature of this ReadMe.

In addition to references cited in the 1992 article, there is now a major subsequent publication on Gurinerdeutsch, Russ (2002), which is the most substantial monograph treatment of the variety. Two parts are of direct relevance to the database: (1) The extensive treatment of the grammar (88–123), which is not, however, without its limitations. In particular, there is no systematic treatment of syntax; while some syntactic points are treated in passing, for others reference must still be made to Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 101–203). One omission relevant to the verbal complex is the lack of explicit discussion of the Resultative Participle (aka Inflected Past Participle), cf. Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 169–170, 200–201) and section 4 below. (2) The texts, including both a selection of earlier written texts (176–192) and the author’s transcriptions of audio-recordings (193–211).

Examples from Gerstner-Hirzel (1979; see also 1982b) and Hotzenköcherle & Brunner (1971) were initially collected by hand by me in the late 1980s by reading through these two sources, and were noted on handwritten slips of paper. In November 2013–February 2014, these examples were digitized into the present database and rechecked against the original sources by Rafael Olivato, working as a student assistant in the then Department of Linguistics, Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Leipzig. Although material from Tomamichel (1982) and Gerstner-Hirzel (1985) was used sporadically in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992), it was not until November–December 2023 that I extracted and digitized the examples from these sources systematically and incorporated them into the database. Although I attempted to collect all relevant examples, I worked by reading through the printed texts, and it is possible that some examples were missed. I subsequently worked through the texts in Gerstner-Hirzel (1982a) and the texts (and other material) in Russ (2002), but did not incorporate material from this source into the database, as this would have involved too significant a departure from the database underlying the original article; however, occasional new construction types found in these sources but absent from the database are included in section 6 below.

I have unfortunately not had the opportunity to visit Bosco Gurin since 1987 and am not in contact with speakers of Gurinerdeutsch, so work since 1987 has been on the basis of material collected before then and publications. This has left some open questions that might be resolved on the basis of additional fieldwork.

The following abbreviations of sources are used to identify examples, accompanied by some combination of line number (l) (i.e. the line in which the example starts), page number (p), section number (s), text number (t):

M Russ (2002): M_Ttt_ll (for texts) or M_Trtrt_ll (for transcriptions);

- R Gerstner-Hirzel (1985): R_s_tt_ll; some texts also have a final letter “a” or “b”; only lines of Gurinerdeutsch text are counted; there is also a brief text in endnote 30 on p.182, and examples from here are identified as R_P182_30_ll
- SD Hotzenköcherle & Brunner (1971): SD_t_lll
- T Tomamichel (1982): T_ppp_ll
- V Gerstner-Hirzel (1979): V_ttt_ll
- VN Gerstner-Hirzel (1982a): VN_tt_ll

Occasionally two examples, perhaps illustrating different points, start in the same line, in which case the context of the discussion should make clear which is intended. Occasionally, the same example illustrates more than one point, in which case it is repeated in the database.

2. Database fields

Each entry in the database consists of the following four fields:

- A. Construction type: The type of verbal complex (see section 3).
- B. Example: The original example in Gurinerdeutsch, using the orthography of the source, but without special formatting (e.g. italics). Note that the different sources use different orthographies.
- C. Literal German translation: Word-by-word transposition of B into Standard German. This thus retains the grammatical structure of B, but uses Standard German vocabulary and morphology.
- D. Source: The source of the example.

Some entries also include include a fifth field:

- E. Comment: This field contains miscellaneous information that might be relevant or interesting, and is not intended to be systematic.

3. Text types

Following Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 126), the following abbreviations are used to identify text types, including in publications by other authors:

- D Diktat (text taken down in writing by the author from the speaker’s oral performance, without the intermediary of an audio recording)
- N Nachdruck (author’s adaptation of a text type S, possibly including changes by the author to reflect more authentic spoken Gurinerdeutsch)

- S Schriftliche Aufzeichnung (speaker’s written performance)
 T Tonbandaufnahme (author’s transcription of the audio recording of a speaker’s oral performance)

4. Constructions with the Past Participle and with the Resultative Participle

A major issue in identifying component order in the Gurinerdeutsch verbal complex is the distinction between the Past Participle (aka Uninflected Past Participle) and the Resultative Participle (aka Inflected Past Participle). The discussion in this section complements that in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1044–1047). The distinction is sufficiently important that I prefer to use the distinct terms Past Participle versus Resultative Participle, as was already done in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992), rather than the more traditional terms Uninflected versus Inflected Past Participle. This also reflects my emphasis on syntactic structures, not just on morphological oppositions, so that all Resultative Participle constructions are identified as such even if they do not have a Resultative Participle form distinct from that of the Past Participle. In all examples in this ReadMe, Resultative Participles are underlined.

A clear instance of the distinction is provided by the Compound Past in (1) versus the Dynamic Passive in (2):

(1) (= construction type 22) (V_180_25)

Gurinerdeutsch	[wènn aswèr appus] hèt ggheert
Literal German translation	[wenn jemand etwas] hat gehört
Standard German translation	[wenn jemand etwas] gehört hat
English translation	[if someone] has heard [something]

(2) (= construction type 50) (V_048_04)

Gurinerdeutsch	[dåss ts Doorf net] <u>pschadiguts</u> choma
Literal German translation	[dass das Dorf nicht] beschädigtes werde
Standard German translation	[dass das Dorf nicht] beschädigt wurde
English translation	[that the village not] be destroyed

The Compound Past uses the Past Participle, which is invariable (in particular, for gender-number), and which in a subordinate clause usually follows the Auxiliary. Given the complete loss of the Simple Past in Gurinerdeutsch, this is the regular grammatical expression of past time reference. The Auxiliary is *ha* ‘haben, have’ or *si* ‘sein, be’, following the same general principles as in other varieties of German: Transitive verbs always take *ha*, intransitive verbs fall into two classes, unaccusatives taking *si*, and unergatives taking *ha*.

The Dynamic Passive uses the Resultative Participle, which agrees in gender-number with the noun phrase to which it refers (whence the Neuter Singular in *pschadiguts* in (2)); since

Gurinerdeutsch does not distinguish Nominative and Accusative cases with nouns and adjectives, there is no difference depending on whether the noun phrase referred to is subject or direct object. In our material, the Resultative Participle always precedes the Auxiliary in a dependent construction (i.e. other than in a main clause). The Resultative Participle occurs in three constructions:

- a) Dynamic Passive (construction types 47–50), with the Auxiliary *chu*, lit. ‘kommen, come’, and corresponding to the Standard German Passive with *werden*.
- b) Resultative Passive (construction types 55–58), typically with the Auxiliary *si* ‘sein, be’, and corresponding to the Standard German Passive with *sein*.
- c) Resultative Active (construction types 51–54), typically with the Auxiliary *si* ‘sein, be’ for unaccusative verbs and *ha* ‘haben, have’ for transitive and unergative verbs.

Unchanged from Comrie & Frauenfelder (1979), I maintain that the Resultative Participle is not a component of the verbal complex. Nonetheless, given the various issues discussed in this section relating to problems distinguishing Resultative Participles from Past Participles, material on verbal sequences including Resultative Participles is included in the database and in the list of construction types in section 6.

Each of the following five criteria (i)–(v) is individually a sufficient criterion for distinguishing a Resultative Participle from the Past Participle of the corresponding verb, although they are not, individually or collectively, necessary criteria:

i) Presence of Rückumlaut (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 169–170, 200–201), a vowel shift that occurs in the Resultative Participle but not in the Past Participle, e.g. Past Participle *ggschtèllt* but Resultative Participle (with Neuter Singular inflection, separated here with a hyphen) *ggschtollt-s*, from *stèlla* ‘stellen, put’. Rückumlaut, however, is only possible with certain verbs, in particular nearly all weak verbs of class I and a number of irregular verbs (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 196, 199). This criterion is not applicable to other verbs.

ii) The Resultative Participle agrees in gender and number with the noun to which it relates. In the conservative variety of Gurinerdeutsch represented in the database, there is a three-way gender distinction in both Singular and Plural, as shown in (3), with representative examples from the database for verbs having a *t*-final and a vowel-final (usually *a*-final, shifting to *n*-final before a vowel-initial suffix) Resultative Participle. Russ (2002: 94–96) discusses the history of the Gurinerdeutsch “strong” adjective inflection, with further references, noting that by the late 20th century the system given in Table 1 had given way to one in which the suffix *-i* is used throughout the plural.

	Masculine	Feminine	Neuter
Singular	-a	-i	-s
	<i>ggfolllt-a</i> 'gefällt, felled'	<i>ggsutzt-i</i> 'gesetzt, put'	<i>zollt-s</i> 'gezählt, counted'
	<i>ggschtorbn-a</i> 'gestorben, died'	<i>ubarfälln-i</i> 'überfallen, attacked'	<i>pessa-s</i> 'gebissen, bitten'
Plural	-Ø	-u	-i
	<i>ggrodlut</i> 'gerüttelt, shaken'	<i>varwändlut-u</i> 'verwandelt, transformed'	<i>varschtokcht-i</i> 'versteckt, hidden'
	<i>punda</i> 'gebunden, tied'	<i>troffn-u</i> 'getroffen, hit'	<i>ggfångn-i</i> 'gefangen, caught'

Table 1: Gender-number Agreement in the Resultative Participle

The fact that the Masculine Plural has a zero suffix means that it is often impossible to distinguish presence of Masculine Plural Agreement from lack of Agreement. However, if the Participle shows Rückumlaut, then of these two possibilities the form is a Resultative Participle with the Masculine Plural zero suffix, as in (3).

(3) (V_157_08)

Gurinerdeutsch	[Schi] sen ... <u>pschtollt</u> ggsin
Literal German translation	[Sie] sind ... bestellt gewesen
Standard German translation	[Sie] sind ... verzaubert gewesen
English translation	[They] have been bewitched

Another context in which Rückumlaut alone is sufficient to identify a form as a Resultative Participle is when a normally transitive verb, thus taking the Auxiliary *ha* 'haben, have' in both the Resultative Active and the Compound Past, is used without a direct object, as in (4) (cf. Comrie & Fraunfelder 1992: 1046). Since there is no direct object for the Resultative Participle to agree with, it remains without any gender-number suffix. However, the form *ggmâât* shows Rückumlaut and is therefore the Resultative Participle, contrasting with the Past Participle *ggmaat* in the Compound Past, as explicitly noted by Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 201).

(4) (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 201)

Gurinerdeutsch	hèscht [scho] <u>ggmää</u> ggaha[, wia dar Tempuràll escht chu]
Literal German translation	hast[-du schon] gemäht gehabt[, als das Gewitter ist gekommen]
Standard German translation	hattest [du schon gemäht[, als das Gewitter gekommen ist] (warst du schon fertig mit Mähen ...)
English translation	had [you already] mown [when the storm came] (had you already finished mowing ...)

Verbs that take the auxiliary *sin* ‘sein, be’ to form the Resultative Active always have a subject, even if this is just the expletive pronoun *as* ‘es, it’, which can therefore trigger Neuter Singular Agreement, as in (5), where the Resultative Participle also shows Rückumlaut (the Infinitive and Past Participle both have the same form *ggschee* ‘geschehen, happen’).

(5) (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 199)

Gurinerdeutsch	[nüw] es[’s] <u>gschoos</u>
Literal German translation	[nun] ist [es] geschehenes
Standard German translation	[nun] ist [es] geschehen
English translation	[now it] has happened

However, Agreement of the Resultative Participle, as of predicative adjectives in general, is usual but not categorical in Gurinerdeutsch, so that there are attested examples of what is otherwise clearly a Resultative Participle but lacking Gender-number Agreement (and Rückumlaut if applicable). Three examples occur in close succession at the end of text V_119, given here as (6)–(8). The speaker is a cat (*Châtzu*, feminine), also referred to as a little animal (*Tiarli*, neuter), the addressee a little girl (*Me’tschi*, neuter). The context is that the girl has failed to carry out the cat’s instructions, as a result of which they are both cursed. However, the Resultative Participle, here as part of the Resultative Passive construction, shows no Agreement, although all genders have an overt suffix in the singular.

(6) (V_119_12)

Gurinerdeutsch	<u>Varflüakcht</u> ben[-i ech]
Literal German translation	Verflucht bin [ich ich]
Standard German translation	Verflucht bin [ich]
English translation	Cursed am [I]

(7) (V_119_12)

Gurinerdeutsch	<u>varflüakcht</u> bescht [düw]
Literal German translation	verflucht bist [du]
Standard German translation	verflucht bist [du]
English translation	cursed are [you]

(8) (V_119_13)

Gurinerdeutsch	[su] we'ti [ech] ggrèttat ggsin
Literal German translation	[so] wäre [ich] gerettet gewesen
Standard German translation	[so] wäre [ich] gerettet gewesen
English translation	[then I] would have been saved

In examples (6)–(8), criterion (iv) below shows that these are Resultative Passive constructions with a Resultative Participle, but the lexical verb form itself shows nothing, since while presence of Agreement is a sufficient criterion for Resultative Participle status, absence of Agreement is a necessary criterion for the Past Participle but is ambivalent for the Resultative Participle.

Table 2 summarizes the above information on whether and how the Resultative Participle can be distinguished from the Past Participle using Agreement and Rückumlaut. The columns distinguish the usual system where Agreement is applied (A–B) and the less usual system where Agreement is not applied (C), with the former subdivided according to whether the verb in question can show Rückumlaut (A) or not (B). The rows distinguish three kinds of trigger: other than Masculine Plural (1), Masculine Plural (MPL) (2), and no trigger (3). Complications arise from the fact that “no visible Agreement” is sometimes ambivalent as between zero Agreement within the Agreement system and no Agreement within the no-Agreement system; if there is also no Rückumlaut, then the Resultative Participle is also indistinguishable morphologically from the Past Participle – other criteria (iii)–(v) below might distinguish the constructions syntactically, but not always so.

		A	B	C
		Agreement		No Agreement
		Rückumlaut available	Rückumlaut unavailable	
1	Trigger other than MPL	Visible Agreement Rückumlaut	Visible Agreement No Rückumlaut	No visible Agreement No Rückumlaut
2	Trigger MPL	No visible Agreement Rückumlaut	No visible Agreement No Rückumlaut	
3	No trigger			

Table 2: Visible Agreement and Rückumlaut in the Resultative Participle

(iii) The auxiliary is neither *ha* ‘haben, have’ nor *sin* ‘sein, be’ (both of which are found in both the Compound Past and Resultative Participle constructions). The most frequent example is *chu*, literally ‘kommen, come’, but used as the Dynamic Passive auxiliary, as in construction types 47–50. However, there is also one example of a Resultative Passive construction (construction type 56) with *plijba* ‘bleiben, remain’ in the auxiliary position, viz. (9).

(9) (V_192_09)

Gurinerdeutsch	[Ech] be [wia am Tesch] <u>ggnâgluta</u> pleba
Literal German translation	[ich] bin [wie am Tisch] genägelt geblieben
Standard German translation	[ich] bin [wie am Tisch] genägelt geblieben
English translation	[I] have remained [as if] nailed [to the table]

(iv) The auxiliary is *sin* ‘sein, be’ and the lexical verb is unequivocally transitive; the construction will then be Resultative Passive (construction type 56, and more generally 55–58). Note that if the lexical verb is ambivalent as to its transitivity (both inchoative and causative, aka labile, aka S=P ambitransitive), then this criterion is not applicable, much as in standard German, with a labile verb like *schmelzen* ‘melt’, *es ist geschmolzen* can be either a Compound Past ‘it has melted’ or a Resultative Passive ‘it is melted’; see V_211_08 for an actual example.

(v) The grammatical subject of the auxiliary is not interpreted as the lexical subject of the lexical verb. There is only one example in the database, viz. (10). The context is that a baby is born with its arms tied – clearly the baby has not tied its own arms.

(10) (V_256_09)

Gurinerdeutsch	... [un] hed [aso t Åârma] <u>punda</u> ggha
Literal German translation	... [und] hat [so die Arme] gebunden gehabt
Standard German translation	... [und] hat [die Arme so] gebunden gehabt
English translation	... [and] has had [its (lit. the) arms] tied [thus]

There is one possible sufficient criterion for identification as a Past Participle, namely that the order with the finite Auxiliary preceding the Participle within the verb complex is found only with Part Participles (construction type 22), never with Resultative Participles (construction type 54). Comrie & Fraunfelder (1992: 1045–1046) note that their Questionnaire respondents rejected the order Auxiliary – Participle for constructions with Resultative Participles. However, placing material after the verbal complex is in general rare, though attested, but rejected in elicitation in Gurinerdeutsch (Comrie & Fraunfelder 1992: 1035–1036), so I would not exclude the possibility that the order rejected by the respondents to the Questionnaire is strongly dispreferred and/or possible only under restricted circumstances rather than absolutely impossible. Incidentally, while the Resultative Participle usually follows components of the verbal complex other than the Dynamic Passive, Resultative Passive, or Resultative Active Auxiliary, there are also examples where it precedes (as noted in the Comments field of the database). Since the Resultative Participle is not a component of the verbal complex, this does not affect generalizations regarding the order of components within the verbal complex.

There remain, however, a number of instances where a construction could in principle be analyzed as either Compound Past or Resultative Active, since none of the criteria (i)–(v) is applicable, though if the Auxiliary precedes the lexical verb then, by the possible criterion noted in the preceding paragraph, the construction is (almost) certainly Compound Past. In addition,

there is, of course, the semantic requirement for the use of the Resultative Active that the construction must be interpretable as resultative (a current state resulting from an earlier event). However, while this can rule out some examples as potential Resultative Actives because there is no possible resultative interpretation, even where a resultative interpretation is possible this does not guarantee that this is the interpretation intended by the speaker, who has the choice in such instances of referring to the earlier event (Compound Past) or the current result (Resultative Active).

A major practical problem here is that, while the order Auxiliary – Past Participle in Compound Past verbal complexes seems to be the original order in Gurinerdeutsch, the opposite order Past Participle – Auxiliary has made considerable inroads, and therefore this latter order cannot be used as a straightforward criterion for identifying Resultative Active constructions (Comrie & Frauenfelder 1992: 1043–1047). The problem is exacerbated by the decision taken explicitly by Gerstner-Hirzel to edit out instances of the Compound Past with the order Past Participle – Auxiliary and replace them with the order Auxiliary – Past Participle, throughout her material (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 15). A striking example is her text V_231, her edited version of a text written by a native speaker. V_231 contains 7 instances of the Compound Past with the order Auxiliary – Past Participle. The original text can be consulted as M_16_36–49, and in each of these 7 instances the original has the order Past Participle – Auxiliary. Note that this is not a criticism of Gerstner-Hirzel's procedure, which is understandable in her aim to present Gurinerdeutsch in a form recognized by speakers as one avoiding most recent influence from Standard German, but it does mean that her texts cannot be used as a basis for evaluating statistically the relative frequency of the two orders in Gurinerdeutsch. There is, however, a rather clear qualitative distinction that arises between spoken and written Gurinerdeutsch, the former as represented in SD and M_Tr, the latter as represented in T and M_T. The spoken texts have overwhelmingly Auxiliary – Past Participle, while the written texts show a sharp shift towards Past Participle – Auxiliary. It is as if the shift to the written medium occasions a shift to the Standard German order in the Compound Past (but hardly at all in other verbal complexes). It is moreover as if Gurinerdeutsch speakers who write their variety are able to control in general lexical, morphological, and phonological parameters (the last as represented in the orthography they select), but less so syntactic parameters. One nice example, this time from spoken Gurinerdeutsch though in the context of responding to prompts in Standard German, is (11), where the speaker first makes both syntactic (order Past Participle – Auxiliary) and lexical (*warda* 'become', cf. Standard German *werden*, but Gurinerdeutsch *chu*) accommodation to Standard German, and then goes on to correct both.

(11) (M_Tr_2_75)

Gurinerdeutsch	[wills tiirär] woordä weitti [wödär] wetti [tiirar tiirar] chu [wödär gmüüruts]
Literal German translation	[weil-es teurer] geworden wäre [als] wäre [teurer teurer] geworden [als gemauertes]
Standard German translation	[weil es teurer] geworden wäre [als gemauert]
English translation	[because it] would become [more expensive than (if) brick-built]

There are some constraints on the composition of the Compound Past in Gurinerdeutsch that go some way towards providing further criteria for distinguishing between Compound Past and Resultative Active. In Gurinerdeutsch, the clearest instances of the Compound Past consist of a finite form of the Auxiliary plus the Past Participle; these finite forms are the Present Indicative (most examples), the Subjunctive I (aka Present Subjunctive, as in R_1_86b_02, V_107_02), and the Subjunctive II (aka Past Subjunctive, as in V_102_08, V_094_11). Russ (2002: 113) claims that Gurinderdeutsch has the “Double” Compound Past, as in many German dialects and colloquial varieties, of the type *ich habe ihm geschrieben gehabt* ‘I had written to him’, literally ‘I have had written to him’. Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 200), by contrast, claims that this “Pluperfect” occurs only in Gurinerdeutsch as a resultative, in my terminology Resultative Active, the analysis also argued for in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1045–1046). Of the three examples provided by Russ (2002: 113), one shows both Rückumlaut and Agreement (Neuter Plural): *abgooti* ‘abgenommen, taken down’, one shows Agreement (Masculine Singular) with a verb that cannot show Rückumlaut: *gmachuta* ‘gemacht, made’, while the third cannot show Rückumlaut and refers to a Masculine Plural noun, whence expected zero Agreement: *üffbygut* ‘aufgestapelt, stacked up’. Two are therefore clearly Resultative Participle constructions, the third is compatible with this analysis and thus provides no evidence for a separate Double Compound Past, nor have I encountered any clear examples of such a construction. This can therefore probably be added as a sixth sufficient criterion for a Resultative Participle as opposed to a Compound Past, namely the presence of the Auxiliary itself in the Compound Past.

Less clear is the possibility of the so-called Perfect Infinitive, i.e. the combination of the Auxiliary of the Compound Past in the Infinitive with the Past Participle of the lexical verb, as in Standard German *er muss gegessen haben* ‘he must have eaten’, *er wird gegessen haben* ‘he will have eaten’, where *gegessen haben* is the Perfect Infinitive. On the one hand, some such constructions seem to be excluded in Gurinerdeutsch because this variety does not make the distinction found in Standard German between deontic and epistemic interpretations of preterito-present modal verbs, e.g. deontic *er hat essen müssen* ‘he had to eat’, i.e. there was some point in the past at which he was obliged to eat, versus epistemic *er muss gegessen haben* ‘he must have eaten’, i.e. I deduce that at some point in the past he ate. Gurinerdeutsch regularly uses the first construction in both deontic and epistemic interpretations; for the latter, see (12).

(12) (V_158_05)

Gurinerdeutsch	[mu] hèt seli ggheera muru
Literal German translation	[man] hat sollen hören murmeln
Standard German translation	[man] soll murmeln gehört haben
English translation	[one] is said to have heard (someone) mumble

Some other apparent instances of the Perfect Infinitive are probably instances of the Resultative Active, as in (13).

(13) (SD_4_024)

Gurinerdeutsch	[Und dē] muäs [mù] <u>gmolchä</u> hä
Literal German translation	[und dann] muss [man] gemolken haben
Standard German translation	[und dann] muss [man] gemolken haben (mit Melken fertig sein)
English translation	[and then one] must have milked (finished milking)

The sense is, from the context, clearly not epistemic. Rather, as explained in a note in the original, it is “mit Melken fertig sein”, i.e. to have finished the milking. Since the auxiliary is *ha* ‘haben, have’ and there is no direct object, there is no possibility of visible Agreement.

However, a small number of examples with the epistemic modal *warda* ‘werden, will’, including one in the database – (14) below – and one cited without source in Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 203) suggest that at least here the Perfect Infinitive is possible, as in (14), where the interpretation is that the speaker is deducing that the referent indulged in the act of ranting and cursing, rather than that the referent was in a state resulting from ranting and cursing (whatever that might be). All of the few examples have the Participle before the Auxiliary *ha* ‘haben, have’.

(14) (V_231_07)

Gurinerdeutsch	[Dèr] werd [ufum Wag ubar 'Tscharantijnar appus] pallud un ggflüachut ha
Literal German translation	[der] wird [auf dem Weg über die Cerentiner etwas] geschimpft und geflucht haben
Standard German translation	[der] wird [auf dem Weg über die Cerentiner etwas] geschimpft und geflucht haben
English translation	[he] will have complained and cursed [somewhat on the way through the Cerentino people]

Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 203) notes that in Gurinerdeutsch the verb *warda* has only this epistemic modal sense, being used neither as the lexical verb ‘werden, become’ (which is *chu*), nor as the Dynamic Passive auxiliary (also *chu*), nor as the Future Auxiliary (no direct correspondent in Gurinerdeutsch). One wonders if even its use as an epistemic modal could be due to the influence of Standard German, though remains purely speculative.

5. Dubious constructions with a Past Participle

Under this heading I subsume a small number of examples in which it is unclear whether a verb form is to be analyzed as an Auxiliary within a single verbal complex, or as a lexical verb (on which a verbal complex may then be dependent). There are two subtypes.

In the first, found with *åfåå* ‘anfangen, begin’ and *heera* (variant: *heera*) ‘hören, hear’ in the Compound Past, the structure is much as when these are Auxiliaries, except that the form is the Past Participle rather than the Infinitive (resulting from what Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1040–1042) call Infinitivization). Compare (15) and (16) with construction types 3 and 18.

(15) (M_T12_11)

Gurinerdeutsch	[unn] hät agfanga [Tetschi] üisspaalta
Literal German translation	[und] hat angefangen [Holzklötze] ausspalten
Standard German translation	[und] hat angefangen, [Holzklötze] auszuspalten
English translation	[and] has begun to split [logs]

(16) (V_228_06)

Gurinerdeutsch	[Ar] hèt ggheert [dü'ssna t Wijbar] zèlla un jååmru
Literal German translation	[er] hat gehört [draußen die Frauen] reden und jammern
Standard German translation	[er] hat [die Frauen draußen] reden und jammern gehört
English translation	[he] has heard [the women] talking and complaining [outside]

Examples like (15)–(16) could simply be a variant of construction types 3 and 18, with the regular Past Participle instead of Infinitivization. However, it is also possible that the use of the regular Past Participle here means that the verb ‘begin’ or ‘hear’ is treated as a lexical verb rather than as an Auxiliary. My inclination is toward the second analysis. Note that the other common verb of perception, *ggsee* ‘sehen, see’, has the same form for Infinitive and Past Participle, so Infinitivization has no visible effect and it is impossible to distinguish possible correspondents of (16) from construction type 18.

The second is found with verbs of motion, with attestations for *gåå* ‘gehen, go’, *chu* ‘kommen, come’, and *ferachu* ‘aufstehen, stand up’. The first subtype parallels the examples with *åfåå* and *heera* above. In the case of *gåå*, the verb form is unequivocally a Past Participle (*ggång-ga*), but this is followed by a pleonastic verb of motion characteristic of verbal complexes, as in (17) (and a handful of other examples in the database). In the case of *chu* Infinitive and Past Participle have the same form anyway, so Infinitivization would not be visible, but still there is the following pleonastic verb of motion, as in (18).

(17) (V_253_17)

Gurinerdeutsch	eschcht [dar Dokchtar dü'ssna] ggång-ga gâ ummarlüaga
Literal German translation	ist [der Arzt draußen] gegangen gehen umherschauen
Standard German translation	ist [der Arzt draußen] gegangen um umherzuschauen [more lit.: ... gegangen, um umherschauen zu gehen]
English translation	[the Doctor] has gone [outside] to go to look around

(18) (V_094_06)

Gurinerdeutsch	[amåål] send[-sch ö ^u w] chu [ema Hü'ss], gâ heischu
Literal German translation	[einmal] sind [sie auch] gekommen [in einem Haus] gehen betteln
Standard German translation	[einmal] sind [sie auch in ein Haus] betteln gekommen [more lit.: ... in ein Haus betteln gehen gekommen]
English translation	[once they] have come [into a house] to go to beg

In the second subtype the verb of motion is in the Infinitive, as expected dependent on a Modal Verb, but is followed by a pleonastic verb of motion. The attested example involves *ferachu* 'aufstehen, stand up', which is a compound of *chu* 'kommen, come' but must be treated as a distinct lexical item since its meaning is not predictable from the meaning of its components.

(19) (V_206_03)

Gurinerdeutsch	[ar] hêt wëlla ferachu chu [t Müis] arschlää
Literal German translation	[er] hat wollen aufstehen kommen [die Maus] erschlagen
Standard German translation	[er] hat aufstehen wollen [um die Maus] zu erschlagen [more lit.: ... um die Maus erschlagen zu kommen]
English translation	[he] has wanted to stand up to (come to) kill [the mouse]

As with the first type, my inclination is to treat the Past Participle (or Infinitive as in (19)) as a lexical verb, with a following verbal complex, rather than as part of the verbal complex. Incidentally, examples like (18), probably also (19) (since *ferachu* is a lexicalized compound whose meaning is not predictable from its parts), question the claim in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1062, n.6) that in Gurinerdeutsch there must always be identity between the main verb and the pleonastic Infinitive, which in turn reopens the question whether pleonastic verbs of motion can be analyzed as particles rather than as verb forms; see also the discussion in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1038) of the example there numbered (16). Further analysis of the constructions in section 5 is required!

6. Construction types

General notes:

1. Each construction type is identified by a number and a formula in the first line of that entry; the formula corresponds to that used in the database. The listing of construction types is

alphabetical, and construction types are numbered accordingly. Since a given construction type may include another as a proper subpart, users of the database should be aware of the frequent need to crossrefer among construction types for completeness.

2. Construction types are divided into four sets: a) 1–42 are those analyzed unequivocally as verbal complexes. b) 43–46 are “dubious”, i.e. I am uncertain whether or not each is an instance of a verbal complex (see section 5 above); the formula is preceded by “D”. c) 47–58 are constructions involving the Resultative Participle (see section 4 above); the formula is preceded by “R”, followed by a classification of the construction type as “Dynamic Passive”, “Resultative Active”, or “Resultative Passive”. d) The fourth set consists of miscellaneous material relevant to the general discussion but not constituting a verbal complex, and is preceded by “Z”; the only numbered construction type in this section is 59.

3. The formula provides a linear representation of the construction type, more specifically of the verbal complex plus, in the case of main clauses, the finite verb. There is no explicit indication of hierarchical structure. Gurinderdeutsch verbal complexes are usually right-branching, with each component in the verbal complex dependent on the immediately preceding component (and the first component dependent on the finite verb in main clauses). Under some construction types, variants are included with variation in component order, as stated explicitly in the Note to that construction type.

4. Section 6 includes for completeness some construction types that are not found in the database, but are attested in other sources (mainly Russ (2002) and the grammatical description in Gerstner-Hirzel (1979: 161–203)).

5. Elements in square brackets are not verbal and are here, for convenience, not treated as part of the verbal complex (in contrast to the decision in Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1032)) or, more generally, of the construction in question. In Gurinderdeutsch, elements that are not part of the verbal complex (such as objects and adverbials) are frequently found between components of the verbal complex and occasionally after the whole verbal complex. See Comrie & Frauenfelder (1992: 1052–1057) for some discussion, though the phenomenon remains in need of systematic investigation; the database provides some material for such a study.

6. The “Standard German translations” occasionally test the boundaries of Standard German, in order better to illustrate the Gurinderdeutsch construction. I have translated the Gurinderdeutsch verb *herta*, frequent in these texts, as Standard German ‘hirten’, English ‘herd’ for convenience, though the sense is more accurately something like carrying out the duties of a cow- or goatherd; see the lemma *hirte* in *Schweizerisches Idiotikon* (vol. 2, col. 1650–1651) – I acknowledge the more general help of this resource in interpreting regional vocabulary.

Abbreviations

@	in a (GerCl, InfCl, SubCl); formulas without this indication are in main clauses
Aux	Auxiliary
CpdPst	Compound Past (Aux <i>ha</i> ‘haben, have’, <i>sin</i> ‘sein, be’)
DynPass	Dynamic Passive (Aux <i>chu</i> ‘werden, be’)
Ger	Gerund (= Standard German Infinitive with <i>zu</i>)

GerCl	Gerund clause
Inf	Infinitive (= Standard German Infinitive without <i>zu</i>)
InfCl	Infinitive clause
Mod	Modal (<i>cheni</i> ‘können, can’, <i>megi</i> ‘mögen/können, may/can’, <i>miassi</i> ‘müssen, must’, <i>seli</i> ‘sollen, should’, <i>terffi</i> ‘dürfen, may’, <i>wella</i> ‘wollen, want’)
Mot	Verb of motion (<i>chu</i> ‘kommen, come’, <i>gåå</i> ‘gehen, go’)
Pass	Passive (Aux Dynamic <i>chu</i> ‘kommen, come’ [= ‘werden, be’], Resultative <i>sin</i> ‘sein, be’)
Perc	Verb of perception (<i>ggsee</i> ‘sehen, see’, <i>ggheara</i> ‘hören, hear’)
Pleo	Pleonastic (<i>chu</i> ‘kommen, come’, <i>gå</i> ‘gehen, go’, <i>lå</i> ‘lassen, cause’, <i>åfå</i> ‘anfangen, begin’) (See Comrie & Frauenfelder 1992: 1038–1039.)
PstPtcp	Past Participle
Res	Resultative (Aux <i>ha</i> ‘haben, have’, <i>sin</i> ‘sein, be’)
ResAct	Resultative Active (Aux <i>ha</i> ‘haben, have’, <i>sin</i> ‘sein, be’)
ResPass	Resultative Passive (Aux <i>sin</i> ‘sein, be’)
ResPtcp	Resultative Participle
SubCl	Finite subordinate clause
V	Verb

1. Aux_åfåå + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wenn’s] afaat aabara (T_148_01)
Literal German translation	[wenn es] anfängt tauen
Standard German translation	[wenn es] zu tauen anfängt
English translation	[when it] begins to thaw

2. Aux_åfåå + Pleo_åfå + Inf [No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[wiar] faaw åfå waarchu (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 202)
Literal German translation	[wir] fangen anfangen arbeiten
Standard German translation	[wir] fangen zu arbeiten an
English translation	[we] begin to work

Note: This structure is given by Gerstner-Hirzel as part of a paradigm, not as a textual example, though our Questionnaire responses confirm the genuineness of the construction (Comrie & Frauenfelder 1992: 1038). It involves loss of the separable prefix *å* on the auxiliary, though not on the pleonastic. There are a few examples in Russ (2002) of the corresponding construction without the pleonastic, as in (2A):

(2A) (M_T3_13)

Gurinerdeutsch	[bald] faat [mu fo] a mäjä
Literal German translation	[bald] fängt [man schon] an mähen
Standard German translation	[bald] fängt [man schon] zu mähen an
English translation	[soon one] begins to mow

3. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_âfâ + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[tüa] he'nt[-sch düa] âfâ jâamru (V_116_09)
Literal German translation	[da] haben [sie da] anfangen jämmern
Standard German translation	[da] haben [sie] zu jämmern angefangen
English translation	[there they] have begun to whine

4. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_âfâ + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	wia ... alls hät afaa waggsaa (T_078_05)
Literal German translation	wie alles hat anfangen wachsen
Standard German translation	[als alles] hat zu wachsen angefangen
English translation	when everything began to grow

5. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_lâ + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[Schi] he'n [tar Dokhtar] lâ chu (V_054_10)
Literal German translation	[Sie] haben [den Doktor] lassen kommen
Standard German translation	[Sie] haben [den Doktor] kommen lassen
English translation	[They] have had [the doctor] come

6. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_lâ + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[dâss ts ândrá ts Schnützpánett héndár ému] het lâ gghijá (R_3_16_07)
Literal German translation	[dass das andere das Taschentuch hinter ihm] hat lassen fallen
Standard German translation	[dass das andere das Taschentuch hinter ihm] hat fallen lassen
English translation	[that the other one] has let [the handkerchief] fall [behind him]

7. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[Wënn-t-sch net] he'n wëlla (V_087_01)
Literal German translation	[Wenn sie nicht] haben wollen
Standard German translation	[Wenn sie nicht] gewollt haben
English translation	[If they] have [not] wanted

Note: This is arguably just a special case of construction type 22, but it is listed separately because of the consistent use of the Infinitive of the Modal Auxiliary (Infinitivization). Compare note on construction type 59.

8. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Aux_lâ + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[fî] hënd [ë net] wellä la gaa (SD_6_011)
Literal German translation	[sie] haben [ihn nicht] wollen lassen gehen
Standard German translation	[sie] haben [ihn nicht] gehen lassen wollen
English translation	[they] have [not] wanted to let [him] go

9. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Aux_leara + Inf

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[Abar] leara schnatzu hatt [i hald glych] wella (M_T12_19)
Literal German translation	[Aber] lernen schnitzen hätte [ich halt gleich] wollen
Standard German translation	[Aber] schnitzen lernen hätte [ich halt gleich] wollen
English translation	[But] to learn to carve [I] would have wanted [immediately]

Note: This example, the only instance encountered of this combination, involves pragmatic fronting of the sequence “Aux_leara + Inf”.

10. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Aux_Mot + Aux_halffa + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	hèt[-sch-mu håltar ö ^w] wëlla gå ... gå halffa [Rijs] assa (V_245_70)
Literal German translation	hat [sie ihm halt auch] wollen gehen helfen [Reis] essen
Standard German translation	hat [sie ihm halt auch Reis] essen helfen gehen wollen
English translation	she has [just also] wanted to go to help him eat [rice]

11. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Aux_Mot + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	han[-i dè amândarscht] miassi gå [gGeiss] trijba (V_154_07)
Literal German translation	habe [ich dann wieder] müssen gehen [die Ziegen] treiben
Standard German translation	habe [ich dann wieder die Ziegen] treiben gehen müssen
English translation	[I] have [again] had to go to drive [the goats]

12. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Aux_Perc + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[mu] hèt seli ggheera muru (V_158_05)
Literal German translation	[man] hat sollen hören murmeln
Standard German translation	[man] hat murmeln hören sollen
English translation	[for: [man] soll murmeln gehört haben] [one] has had to hear murmur [for: one is said to have heard murmuring]

13. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[aar] hèt [düa] cheni flia (V_028_04)
Literal German translation	[er] hat [da] können fliehen
Standard German translation	[er] hat [da] fliehen können
English translation	[he] has [there] been able to flee

14. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	wia-sch dâs Chenn he'n wëlla teata (V_205_01)
Literal German translation	[als sie das Kind] haben wollen töten
Standard German translation	[als sie das Kind] haben töten wollen
English translation	[when they] have wanted to kill [the child]

15. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mot + Aux_halffa + Inf

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[Er] eſt ... ga hälfe [d geiss] hertu (M_T4_10)
Literal German translation	[Er] ist gehen helfen [die Ziegen] hirten
Standard German translation	[Er] ist gegangen zu helfen, [die Ziegen] zu hirten
English translation	[He] has gone to help herd [the goats]

16. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mot + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[... und] escht [ö ^w] gå maaja (V_229_25)
Literal German translation	[... und] ist [auch] gehen mähen
Standard German translation	[... und] ist auch mähen gegangen
English translation	[... and] has [also] gone to mow

17. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mot + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wènn-t- 's dè med iasch] escht chu weldschu (V_188_01)
Literal German translation	[wenn es dann mit uns] ist kommen spielen
Standard German translation	[wenn es dann mit uns] spielen gekommen ist
English translation	[when it then] has come to play [with us]

18. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Perc + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[tarnåå] he'nt[-sch ts Chenn] ggheara weinu (V_027_04)
Literal German translation	[danach] haben [sie das Kind] hören weinen
Standard German translation	[danach] haben sie [das Kind] weinen gehört
English translation	[afterwards they] have heard [the child] cry

19. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Perc + Inf @SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[dia, wå-sch] he'in ggsea chu (V_153_07)
Literal German translation	[die, wo sie] haben sehen kommen
Standard German translation	[die, die sie] haben kommen gesehen
English translation	[those who] have seen [them] come

20. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_tian + Ger

Gurinerdeutsch	[tè] hèt[-ar 's] tian z ragnun (V_255_05)
Literal German translation	[da] hat [er es] tun zu regnen
Standard German translation	[da] hat [er es] zu regnen veranlasst
English translation	[then he] has caused [it] to rain

21. Aux_CpdPst + Aux_tian + Ger @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wå dè] hèt tian [ti grooss Ggloggu] z litan (V_231_03)
Literal German translation	[der da] hat veranlassen [die große Glocke] zu läuten
Standard German translation	[der da] [die große Glocke] zu läuten veranlasst hat
English translation	[who there] has caused [the big bell] to ring

22. Aux_CpdPst + PstPtcp @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wènn aswèr appus] hèt ggheert (V_180_25)
Literal German translation	[wenn jemand etwas] hat gehört
Standard German translation	[wenn jemand etwas] gehört hat
English translation	[if someone] has heard [something]

23. Aux_halffa + Inf @ GerCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[fer mar] halffa z holzun (V_170_01)
Literal German translation	[um mir] helfen zu holzen
Standard German translation	[um mir] zu helfen zu holzen
English translation	[in order] to help [me] to get wood

Note: The Gerund is licensed by the purposive particle *fer*, not by the Auxiliary *halffa*, which always takes an Infinitive Clause (Infinitive without *zu*) in the Gurinerdeutsch material familiar to me.

24. Aux_låå + Inf @ GerCl

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[ooni suscht niama nit] la z'wessen (M_T7_12)
Literal German translation	[ohne sonst niemand nichts] lassen zu wissen
Standard German translation	[ohne sonst jemand etwas] wissen zu lassen
English translation	[without otherwise] letting [anyone] know [anything]

25. Aux_låå + Pleo_lå + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[dy] läåw[är em lanngsi] la gaa (SD_3_006)
Literal German translation	[die] lassen[-wir im Frühling] (lassen) gehen
Standard German translation	[die] lassen [wir im Frühling] gehen
English translation	[we] let [them] go [in the spring]

26. Aux_Mod + Aux_åfå + Inf

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[wiar] chunu åfå waarchu (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 202)
Literal German translation	[wir] können anfangen arbeiten
Standard German translation	[wir] können zu arbeiten anfangen
English translation	[we] can begin to work

27. Aux_Mod + Aux_lå + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[mu] sællti [kChenn net] lå züalüaga (V_205_14)
Literal German translation	[man] sollte [die Kinder nicht] lassen zusehen
Standard German translation	[man] sollte [die Kinder nicht] zusehen lassen
English translation	[one] should [not] let [the children] watch

28. Aux_Mod + Aux_Mot + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[Ech] müass [moora] gå [ts Gaalt] gea (V_252_21)
Literal German translation	[Ich] muss [morgen] gehen [das Geld] holen
Standard German translation	[Ich] muss [morgen das Geld] holen gehen
English translation	[I] must go [tomorrow] to fetch [the money]

29. Aux_Mod + Aux_Mot + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[as chlijs Chenn, tâs as åålt's Wip] sèllti gå fenda (V_033_05)
Literal German translation	[ein kleines Kind, das eine alte Frau] sollte gehen finden
Standard German translation	[ein kleines Kind, das eine alte Frau] finden gehen sollte
English translation	[a small child that] should go to find [an old woman]

30. Aux_Mod + Aux_tian + Ger

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[düw] sèlltischt[-na] tian z assan (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 202)
Literal German translation	[du] solltest [ihn] veranlassen zu essen
Standard German translation	[du] solltest [ihn] zu essen veranlassen
English translation	[you] should make [him] eat

31. Aux_Mod + Inf @ InfCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[ùm dry] misi üff'taa (SD_4_063)
Literal German translation	[um drei] müssen aufstehen
Standard German translation	[um drei] aufstehen müssen
English translation	must get up [at three]

Note: Both examples in the database lack a finite verb (“Insubordination”).

32. Aux_Mod + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wå-sch kChelchu] wèlla büwwa (V_047_02)
Literal German translation	[wo sie die Kirche] wollen bauen
Standard German translation	[wo sie die Kirche] bauen wollen
English translation	[where they] want to build [the church]

Note: See T_121_28 for an unusual inversion of this order.

33. Aux_Mot + Inf @ GerCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[fer dâs Loch] gå z lüagan (V_117_07)
Literal German translation	[um das Loch] gehen zu sehen
Standard German translation	[um das Loch] sehen zu gehen
English translation	[in order to] go to see [the hole]

34. Aux_Mot + Inf @ InfCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[düw] chu hertu (V_105_16)
Literal German translation	[du] kommen hirten
Standard German translation	[du und] [die Kühe] hirten kommen
English translation	[you] come to herd [the cows]?!

Note: Judging from the free German translation given in the source “du und hirten!”, this is a use of grammatical “Insubordination” to express sarcasm, i.e. the construction is an Infinitive Clause without a Main Clause. This takes *chu* to be the Infinitive form.

35. Aux_Mot + Pleo_Mot + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[tè] chun[-i dè moora] chu [ts Gaalt] gea (V_252_17)
Literal German translation	[dann] komme [ich dann morgen] kommen [das Geld] holen
Standard German translation	[dann] komme [ich morgen das Geld] holen
English translation	[then I] come [tomorrow] to fetch [the money]

36. Aux_Mot + Pleo_Mot + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wènn-t-schi di Chia] geng-ga gå varschtèkcha (V_003_06)
Literal German translation	[wenn sie die Kühe] gehen (gehen) verstecken
Standard German translation	[wenn sie die Kühe] verstecken gehen
English translation	[when they] go to hide [the cows]

37. Aux_Perc + Inf @ SubCl [No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[wia wennmu euch] ghearti zella (M_T6_12)
Literal German translation	[wie wenn-man euch] hörte erzählen
Standard German translation	[wie wenn man euch] erzählen hörte
English translation	[as if one] would hear [you] tell

38. Aux_tian + Ger @ GerCl
[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[fer schi alli] tian [dre] z'gschtaan (M_T12_42)
Literal German translation	[um sie alle] veranlassen [drin] zu-stehen
Standard German translation	[um sie alle] zu veranlassen [drin] zu stehen
English translation	[in order to] make [them all] stand [in it]

Note: The single instance of *z* serves as licensee of both *fer* and *tian*.

39. Aux_tian + Pleo_tian + Ger
[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[düw] tüascht[-na] tian z assan (Gerstner-Hirzel 1979: 202)
Literal German translation	[du] veranlässt [ihn] veranlassen zu essen
Standard German translation	[du] veranlässt [ihn] veranlassen zu essen
English translation	[you] make [him] eat

40. Aux_tüa + Inf @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wia wènn-n-isch appus] taati riapfa [metta Hèndu] (V_085_05)
Literal German translation	[wie wenn uns etwas] täte rufen [mit den Händen]
Standard German translation	[wie wenn uns etwas mit den Händen] riefte
English translation	[as if something] did summon [us with its hands]

Note: See V_231_07 for an unusual inversion of this order (in the original, but amended by Gerstner-Hirzel).

41. Aux_waarda + Aux_Mod + Inf
[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	nüw wurd-i miassi schtaarba (VN_47_15)
Literal German translation	nun würde ich müssen sterben
Standard German translation	nun würde ich sterben müssen
English translation	now I would have to die

Note: See also construction type 42. The Auxiliary *waarda* is presumably epistemic. Gerstner-Hirzel translates with the Present in Standard German: *nun werde ich sterben müssen* ‘now I will have to die’ (i.e. ‘I assume I must die’).

42. Aux_waarda + PstPtcp + Aux_CpdPst

Gurinerdeutsch	[Dèr] werd [ufum Wag ubar 'Tscharantijnar appus] pallud un ggflüachut ha (V_231_07)
Literal German translation	[Der] wird [auf dem Weg über die Cerentiner etwas] geschimpft und geflucht haben
Standard German translation	[Der] wird [auf dem Weg über die Cerentiner etwas] geschimpft und geflucht haben
English translation	[He] will have complained and cursed [somewhat on the way through the Cerentino people]

Note: See discussion of Auxiliary *waarda* in section 4.

43. D: Aux_CpdPst + åfåå_PstPtcp + Inf

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	[unn] hät agfanga [Tetschi] üisspaalta (M_T12_11)
Literal German translation	[und] hat angefangen [Holzklötze] ausspalten
Standard German translation	[und] hat angefangen, [Holzklötze] auszuspalten
English translation	[and] has begun to split [logs]

Note: Compare construction type 3.

44. D: Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + Mot_PstPtcp + Pleo_Mot + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[ar] hèt wèlla ferachu chu [t Müis] arschlåå (V_206_03)
Literal German translation	[er] hat wollen aufstehen kommen [die Maus] erschlagen
Standard German translation	[er] hat aufstehen wollen [um die Maus] zu erschlagen
English translation	[he] has wanted to stand up to kill [the mouse]

45. D: Aux_CpdPst + Mot_PstPtcp + Pleo_Mot + Inf (V_253_17)

Gurinerdeutsch	escht [dar Dokchtar] dü'ssna ggång-ga gå ummarlüaga (V_253_17)
Literal German translation	ist [der Arzt draußen] gegangen gehen umherschauen
Standard German translation	ist [der Arzt draußen] gegangen um umherzuschauen
English translation	[more lit.: ... gegangen, um umherschauen zu gehen] [the Doctor] has gone [outside] to go to look around

46. D: Aux_CpdPst + Perc_PstPtcp + Inf

Gurinerdeutsch	[Ar] hèt ggheert [dü'ssna t Wijbar] zèlla un jåàmru (V_228_06)
Literal German translation	[er] hat gehört [draußen die Frauen] reden und jammern
Standard German translation	[er] hat [die Frauen draußen] reden und jammern gehört
English translation	[he] has heard [the women] talking and complaining [outside]

47. R: Dynamic Passive: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_DynPass

Gurinerdeutsch	[Schia escht] <u>ubarfällni</u> chu (V_015_06)
Literal German translation	[Sie ist] überfallene geworden
Standard German translation	[Sie ist] überfallen worden
English translation	[She has] been attacked

48. R: Dynamic Passive: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_DynPass @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[be(s) 's asoo] escht <u>pessas</u> chu (V_229_28)
Literal German translation	[bis es so] ist gebissenes geworden
Standard German translation	[bis es so] gebissen worden ist
English translation	[until it] is bitten [thus]

49. R: Dynamic Passive: Aux_Mod + ResPtcp + Aux_DynPass @ SubCl

[No examples in database]

Gurinerdeutsch	dass z'ganz Volch im römische Rych miassi <u>zollt's</u> chu (M_T13_01)
Literal German translation	[dass das-ganze Volk im römischen Reich] muss gezähltes werden
Standard German translation	[dass das ganze Volk im römischen Reich] gezählt werden muss
English translation	[that the whole people in the Roman Empire] must be counted

50. R: Dynamic Passive: ResPtcp + Aux_DynPass @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[dåss ts Doorf net] <u>pschadiguts</u> choma (V_048_04)
Literal German translation	[dass das Dorf nicht] beschädigtes werde
Standard German translation	[dass das Dorf nicht] beschädigt wurde
English translation	[that the village not] be destroyed

51. R: Resultative Active: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_ResAct

Gurinerdeutsch	[tar Schnetzar hèt 's scho] <u>gglu</u> fta ggha (V_205_11)
Literal German translation	[das Messer hat es schon] gehobenes gehabt
Standard German translation	[das Messer hat es schon] gehoben gehabt
English translation	[it has already] had the knife [raised]

Note: Gurinerdeutsch *Schnetzar* ‘Messer, knife’ is masculine, whence the Masculine form of the ResPtcp.

Gurinerdeutsch	[as escht scho gânz] <u>varjas</u> uts ggsin (V_219_09)
Literal German translation	[es ist schon ganz] verwestes gewesen
Standard German translation	[es ist schon ganz] verwest gewesen
English translation	[it has already] been quite decomposed

52. R: Resultative Active: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_ResAct @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[dâs-ar] escht <u>ggschtorb</u> na ggsin (V_185_05)
Literal German translation	[dass er] ist gestorbener gewesen
Standard German translation	[dass er] gestorben war (lit. gewesen ist)
English translation	[that he] has been dead

53. R: Resultative Active: Aux_Mod + ResPtcp + Aux_ResAct

Gurinerdeutsch	[Und dē] muäs [mù] <u>gmolch</u> ä hä (SD_4_024)
Literal German translation	[Und dann] muss [man] gemolken haben
Standard German translation	[Und dann] muss [man] gemolken haben (= mit Molken fertig sein)
English translation	[And then one] must have milked (= have finished milking)

54. R: Resultative Active: ResPtcp + Aux_ResAct @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	Wën wär <u>gmolch</u> ä hew (SD_1_027)
Literal German translation	wenn wir gemolken haben
Standard German translation	wenn wir gemolken haben (= mit Molken fertig sind)
English translation	when we have milked (= have finished milking)

55. R: Resultative Passive: Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod + ResPtcp + Aux_ResPass

Gurinerdeutsch	[Dåå] hèt seli [a Fållu] ggschtolli sin (V_032_03)
Literal German translation	[Da] hat sollen [eine Falle] gestellte sein
Standard German translation	[Da] sollte [eine Falle] gestellt sein
English translation	[There it] was said [that a trap] was set

56. R: Resultative Passive: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_ResPass

Gurinerdeutsch	[as escht dre] ggsutzts ggsin (V_089_05)
Literal German translation	[es ist drin] gesetztes gewesen
Standard German translation	[es ist darin] gesetzt gewesen
English translation	[it has] been placed [inside]

57. R: Resultative Passive: Aux_CpdPst + ResPtcp + Aux_ResPass @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[wellsch in metschar Nacht eistar] senn <u>gstoorti</u> gsinn (T_077_19)
Literal German translation	[weil-sie in mitten Nacht immer] sind gestörte gewesen
Standard German translation	[weil sie mitten in der Nacht immer] gestört gewesen sind
English translation	[because they] have [always] been disturbed [in the middle of the night]

58. R: Resultative Passive: ResPtcp + Aux_ResPass @ SubCl

Gurinerdeutsch	[bés ålli] gg <u>fångni</u> sén (R_3_15a_04)
Literal German translation	[bis alle] gefangene sind
Standard German translation	[bis alle] gefangen sind
English translation	[until all] are caught

59. Z: Aux_CpdPst + Aux_Mod

Gurinerdeutsch	[Ar] hét [net Waltsch] cheni (V_058_19)
Literal German translation	[Er] hat [nicht Italienisch] können
Standard German translation	[Er] hat [nicht Italienisch] gekonnt
English translation	[He] has [not] been able (to speak) Italian

Note: Arguably just a special case of Aux_CpdPst + PstPtcp, i.e. the Compound Past, but it is listed separately because of the consistent use of the Infinitive of the Modal Auxiliary (Infinitivization). Compare note on construction type 7.

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